

Recommended citation: Weidle, F., Seidel, A., Börner, C., Flagmeier, L., & Vossler, J. (2019). Dealing with diversity - Co-designing a game-based learning scenario in engineering studies. In Nagyn, B. V., Murphy, M., Järvinen, H.-M., & Kálmán, A. (Eds.), *Varietas delectat... Complexity is the new normality. SEFI 47th Annual Conference* (pp. 1010-1021). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Budapest, Hungary. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14656627.

Dealing with Diversity

Co-designing a Game-based Learning Scenario in Engineering Studies

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Conference Key Areas: Diversity in Engineering Education, Integrated learning environments for the digital native learners

Keywords: Engineering Education, Game-based Learning, Engineering Mechanics, User-centred Design

ABSTRACT

Lecturers are confronted with diversifying student bodies. Different admission restrictions allow students to enter institutions of higher education with varying educational backgrounds. Moreover, current internationalization strategies at German universities attract an increasing number of students from abroad. This results in varying knowledge levels and language skills that need to be addressed in the conceptualization of teaching formats and materials.

Engineering mechanics presents a challenge to a high number of students, as it is evidenced by weak examination performance. As a basic subject in most engineering programmes, learning and comprehension problems in this area, however, not only lead to failure in exams but could also create substantial knowledge gaps over the course of one's studies. One possibility to tackle these issues is the adoption of a game-based learning (GBL) approach. GBL presents a promising tool for mediating abstract content because of its motivating and cognitive effects. Moreover, adaptive elements can respond to the different needs, interests and habits of a diversifying student body.

The Learn&Play project presented here utilizes a participative user-centred design approach to develop a sustainable learning scenario for engineering mechanics that focuses on motivation, interest, learning strategies and comprehension as important factors for academic achievement. The concept paper will outline the results of the project's underlying problem analysis and illustrate the benefits of GBL in the context of the demands and challenges posed by engineering education in an increasingly digital, international and, thus, complex world.

1 INTRODUCTION

The tech industry is an interesting job market. This is evidenced by the high amount of enrolments in engineering courses each semester. However, the initial interest of students appears striking in the face of the high dropout rates in undergraduate courses at German universities and technical colleges (1). Problems are regarded to

stem from the transition to the Bologna-system, insufficient prior knowledge, the abstract nature of the subject matter as well as differing educational backgrounds (2). At the Brandenburg University of Technology Cottbus-Senftenberg (BTU), the student body is especially diverse. Here, students can choose between an integrated, university and college degree program. Moreover, with up to 50% of students speaking German as a second language, various linguistic proficiencies, educational and cultural backgrounds as well as knowledge levels coalesce.

Weak exam results are indicative of the challenges posed by the basic subject of engineering mechanics (EM) (3). Due to its central role in engineering studies, learning and comprehension problems in this area can not only lead to failure in exams but also cause fundamental knowledge gaps over the course of the study programme. Sources for low academic achievement are seen in the high level of abstraction, the following of strictly specified rules and procedures, insufficient prior knowledge and a low level of self-regulation (3). Keeping the diverse student body in mind, these challenges need to be considered and directly addressed in the instructional design of learning content.

2 THEORY

2.1 Diversity

Under-representation of women and ethnic minorities is a general problem in engineering studies. Adelman (4) stressed already twenty years ago that universities should place more emphasis on minorities by mirroring a rather balanced workforce, which allows graduates to communicate with a heterogeneous clientele, and representing socio-cultural diversity. Moreover, the numbers of women in STEM-studies have been declining since 2006 despite the high demand for qualified graduates (5). However, studying STEM seems unattractive to women because of its traditional focus and portrayal as male study field, cultural discrimination against female students and different learning behaviour as well as an emphasis on rather male teaching methods in school and university (5).

2.2 Learning Strategies

To study at a university implies structuring the process of learning in a self-regulatory way. But which learning strategies (LS) do students apply in their study of EM and which of those are more efficient than others? LS are defined as sets of behaviour directed towards a learning task (6). Wild clusters LS in cognitive and meta-cognitive strategies as well as resources (7). Cognitive LS can be divided into deeply and superficially cognitive LS and are described as processes which are connected to information acquisition, processing and storing. Meta-cognitive LS direct the active and self-aware control and regulation of learning processes such as the planning, observing and adjusting of one's learning behaviour. Resources are linked to processes that structure learning as a whole such as concentration or cooperative learning. Although every LS is important in its own right, gathering and storing information is necessary for all of them which is why Wild suggests the use of cognitively deep LS for gaining a more in depth understanding of complex concepts (8).

2.3 Game-based Learning

Game-based learning (GBL) describes a learning environment in which learning processes are supported by narrative, immersive, adaptive, competitive, cooperative

and other game elements (9). The aim is to transfer the principle of hard but satisfying labour, which leads to a sense of achievement and, ultimately, the experience of pleasure or fun, onto the learning experience. By carefully selecting and combining game elements such as digital storytelling and reward systems, affective, motivational, cognitive and socio-cultural factors can be stimulated (10), which has the potential to increase students' interest in the subject matter (11) and eventually steer them towards a greater engagement with the learning content (11).

According to Wouters and Van Oostendorp, GBL can take on different functions during the learning process: 1) It can prepare future learning, 2) teach new knowledge and skills, 3) train existing knowledge and skills and 4) convey skills of the 21st century (11). Nevertheless, the learning success associated with GBL, its respective purpose and design depends on a variety of factors and has become subject to critical debate (12). The increased time investment and unbalanced emphasis of game and educational objectives (13, 14) are often discussed as central problems. Since more situated analysis is needed to understand the interplay between gaming and learning, the project presented here makes a significant contribution to the current state of research in this area.

3 OBJECTIVES OF THIS STUDY

The aim of Learn&Play is to develop a GBL scenario that prepares engineering students for the challenges posed by EM during the first semesters. In the initial phase of the user research conducted in the context of this project, specific problem areas related to differing knowledge levels, learning processes and content were identified in order to devise concept ideas for a suitable scenario. The suitability of the scenario will be determined by and evaluated according to its capacity to positively affect the learning experience cognitively, motivationally, behaviourally and socio-culturally over the long term. To ensure the suitability, sustainability and integration of the scenario into established teaching and learning structures the developers seek to work closely with the respective target groups including a set of prospective students, beginners and lecturers as diverse as possible.

The following questions and objectives were vital in directing the user research:

1. How motivated are students to engage with EM? Do factors such as gender, language and educational background play a significant role in the extent to which students are motivated?
2. Which attitude towards EM do students display? Does the attitude differ regarding to gender, language and educational background?
3. Which types of LS do students use? Do the LS differ regarding to gender, language and educational backgrounds?
4. What kinds of problems do students face while learning EM? Do the learning problems differ regarding to gender, language and educational backgrounds?

4 METHOD

4.1 Participants, Materials and Procedure

Over the period of one month, an exploratory survey was conducted with 154 engineering students of universities and technical colleges in Brandenburg, Berlin and Saxony (16 women, 1 diverse, 13 not defined: $M = 21.61$ years, $SD = 3.34$). Students could participate via an online questionnaire that was mainly distributed via social media platforms including respective student groups on Facebook.

Additionally, a paper version was handed out at the end of three EM lectures at BTU and the University of Applied Sciences Dresden. As an incentive for their voluntary participation, students had the chance to win one of four 15€ gift vouchers.

The digital as well as the paper questionnaire contained twelve questions addressing aspects of motivation, attitude, learning strategies and learning problems in regard to EM. Furthermore, it gathered demographical variables including age, gender, educational background and first language.

4.2 Measures

Motivation was described by adapting six items of the *Expectancy-value-Form of Domain-Specific Learning Motivation Questionnaire* (EWF-LM) (15). The concept was divided into activity-based motivation including statements such as “I enjoy dealing with content related to engineering mechanics” and content-specific motivation including statements such as “I think content related to engineering mechanics is boring”. Answers were given according to a five-point Likert scale between 1 (“not at all”) and 5 (“absolutely”). Negatively coded items have been recoded for analysis. In order to calculate the motivation average value the three sub-items of each motivation type were added together and then divided by three.

The attitude towards engineering content in general and EM in particular was measured via a five-point Likert scale. Participants were asked to rate the importance of EM in their daily life by assigning values between 1 (“Not important at all”) and 5 (“Very important”).

LS were assessed using an open question as well as a multiple choice format. First, students were asked to describe the preparation for their last EM exam. They could then choose among a given set of LS they preferably applied. The list of examples were devised according to the learning strategy classification by Schiefe and Wild (16) and, thus, included cognitive (“I learn content by heart”) and meta-cognitive LS (“I ask myself which is the best strategy in order to reach my objective”) as well as resources (“I make a timetable”). Answers to the open question were coded according to the LS cluster (8).

To measure personal learning problems in EM participants were asked to describe both, general as well as more specific problems they usually face during the study of EM. Answers were coded in a semi-open way following inductively devised categories and cross-checked by a second rater.

5 RESULTS

5.1 Motivation

To assess differences in motivation regarding gender, language and educational background, a one-way ANOVA was conducted. Because the assumption of a normal distribution was violated, a Kruskal-Wallis-Test was conducted.

Table 1. Means and standard deviations of motivation regarding gender, language and educational background

Variable	N	Content-specific motivation		Activity-based motivation	
		<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>
In total	152	3.84	1.03	3.19	0.86
Female	16	3.4	1.22	2.92	1.08
Male	124	3.93	0.95	3.24	0.81
German as first language	127	3.89	0.99	3.21	0.84
German not as first language	11	3.88	0.86	3.3	0.95
A-levels/high school diploma	101	3.82	1	3.16	0.86
Technical diploma, professional training	39	4.03	0.96	3.33	0.8

No differences were found regarding content-specific motivation in gender ($H(1) = 2.71, p = 1$), language ($H(1) = 0.01, p = .91$) or educational background ($H(1) = 1.39, p = .24$). Furthermore, no differences were found regarding activity-based motivation in gender ($H(1) = 0.96, p = .33$), language ($H(1) = 0, p = 1$) or educational background ($H(1) = 1.66, p = .19$).

5.2 Attitude

To assess differences in attitudes regarding gender, language and educational background, a one-way ANOVA was conducted. The variables do not mirror a normal distribution. Thus, a Kruskal-Wallis-Test was conducted instead.

Table 2. Means and standard deviations of attitudes regarding gender, language and educational background

Variable	N	Attitude engineering science		Attitude EM in studies		Attitude EM in daily life	
		<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>
In total	152	4.19	1.1	3.97	1.12	3.44	1.14
Female	16	3.95	1.13	3.88	1.15	2.88	1.45
Male	124	4.3	0.99	4.05	1.06	3.56	1.04
German as first language	127	4.27	1.03	4.11	1.02	3.52	1.11
German not as first language	11	4.27	0.65	3.55	1.29	3.27	1.01

A-levels/high school diploma	101	4.21	1	3.94	1.05	3.43	1.13
Technical diploma, professional training	39	4.38	1.02	4.26	1.1	3.64	1.06

No difference in attitude towards engineering science was found in gender ($H(1) = 2.05, p = .15$), language ($H(1) = 0.5, p = .48$) or educational background ($H(1) = 1.72, p = .19$). Neither were there differences in attitude towards EM in study programmes regarding gender ($H(1) = 0.3, p = .58$) or language ($H(1) = 2.61, p = .11$). However, a difference was identified related to educational background ($H(1) = 4.68, p = .03$). Results concerning attitude towards EM in daily life show no difference related to gender ($H(1) = 3.16, p = .075$), language ($H(1) = 0.52, p = .47$) or educational background ($H(1) = 1.03, p = .31$).

5.3 Learning Strategies

Differences in frequencies of LS adopted by students regarding gender, language and educational background were assessed via a chi-square test with two questions. Expected cell frequencies under five were assessed via Fisher’s exact test. The open question “How did you prepare for your last EM exam?” showed differences in the use of cognitively deep LS in gender (Fisher’s exact test, $p = .01, \phi = .25$), language (Fisher’s exact test, $p = .02, \phi = -.25$) and educational background (Fisher’s exact test, $p = .01, \phi = .24$). Another difference was found in the use of meta-cognitive LS for gender (Fisher’s exact test, $p < .001, \phi = .32$). The most noted LS were of the cognitively superficial type (109 times), followed by cognitively deep LS (29 times), resources (18times) and meta-cognitive LS (18 times).

Table 3. Frequencies of LS according to gender, language and educational background (open)

	cognitively deep					cognitively superficial					meta-cognitive					resources				
	1	0	x2	p	ϕ	1	0	x2	p	ϕ	1	0	x2	p	ϕ	1	0	x2	p	ϕ
gender																				
male	21	90		.01	.25	14	2		.74	.07	11	103		0	.32	1	15		.69	.07
female	8	8				90	14				7	9				16	98			
language																				
1.	24	96		.02	.25	95	25		1	.05	17	103		1	.01	16	104		1	.01
2.	5	3				7	1				1	7				1	7			
education																				
A-levels	27	68	7,61	.01	.24	76	19	0	1	.00	16	79		.15	.14	14	81		.78	.04
diploma	2	33				28	7				2	33				4	31			

Answers provided for the multiple choice question showed a different use of LS regarding language and resources (fisher’s exact test, $p = .01, \phi = .24$). Cognitively

superficial (122 times) and cognitively deep LS (128 times) were indicated the most, followed by resources (84 times) and meta-cognitive LS (67 times).

Table 4. Frequencies of LS regarding gender, language and educational background (multiple choice)

	cognitively deep					cognitively superficial					meta-cognitive					resources				
	1	0	x2	ρ	φ	1	0	x2	ρ	φ	1	0	x2	ρ	φ	1	0	x2	ρ	φ
gender																				
female	15	0		.22	.13	13			1	.03	7	8	0	1	0	8	8	0,56	.45	.45
male	106	16				102					57	65				73	49			
language																				
1.	110	14		1	.02	107			.21	.10	57	67	0	.97	0	77	48		.01	.24
2.	10	1				8					5	6				2	9			
education																				
A-levels	89	9		.24	.12	82	16	0,02	.89	.01	41	57	3,29	.07	.16	55	44	1,43	.23	.10
diploma	32	7				33	6				23	16				26	13			

5.4 Learning Problems in Engineering Mechanics

A chi-square test was used to assess differences regarding the frequencies of gender, language and educational background. All expected cell frequencies were under five, which is why Fisher's exact test was conducted. No differences were found regarding to gender, language and educational background. Figure 1 shows the general frequencies of the answers provided by participants.

Fig. 1. Frequencies of learning problems in EM

Among the most frequent problems were the identification of appropriate solution procedures (22 times), the tangibility of the content (11times), the allotted time and workload (10 times), arithmetic operations including vectors and equation systems (8 times), too vague or incomprehensible instructions (8 times), the complexity of the content (8 times) and the retrospective reviewing of content (8 times).

6 SUMMARY AND IMPLICATIONS

The aim of the questionnaire was to gather initial information about engineering students' motivational levels, their attitudes towards EM and engineering sciences in general as well as their use of different LS and specific learning problems they face in EM. In addition, differences related to gender, language and educational backgrounds were assessed.

Content-specific and activity-based motivation are generally above average. Differences regarding gender, language and educational background were not found.

Overall, students appeared to be more interested in the content itself and less in actually engaging with it. This is not least due to the fact that the abstract and complex nature of the learning content often leads to comprehension and application problems. All students rated engineering in general and EM as part of engineering as important. Students with technical diplomas rated the importance of EM in the context of their studies as more important than students coming straight out of grammar school. There were no further differences found related to gender, language or educational background.

According to the answers given to the open question, cognitively superficial LS are applied the most, whereas cognitively deep LS, resources and meta-cognitive LS are less frequently used. Moreover, female students, students speaking German as a second (or third) language and students with a grammar school background use cognitively deep LS more often than others. Women also showed a higher usage of meta-cognitive LS. In contrast, ranking LS according to the provided list, cognitively superficial and deep LS are used the most, followed by resources and meta-cognitive LS. Students speaking German as a second (or third) language use less resources than native speakers. Since resources are usually provided in German, they may present a higher threshold for international students. Reasons for these results could thus lie in accessibility and language skills.

Learning problems frequently noted referred to solution procedures, the tangibility and complexity of the content, time and workload, basic arithmetic operations including vectors and equation systems, reviewing content retrospectively and the nature of the instructions provided. With its various functionalities, GBL offers different starting points for tackling these problems. According to the respective demands and objectives, GBL can be put to use at different points throughout the course of a study programme. In its orientation to support future learning it would be suitable as a tool to prepare students for an engineering study programme in general as well as a particular module or lecture by raising, for example, the activity-based motivation of prospective students. Furthermore, prior knowledge especially in mathematics, which was a noted problem in this study, could be trained in an interactive and playful way so that students are prepared better and feel more engaged. The content mediated and trained within a game-based learning scenario can be transferred onto the dissemination of knowledge in lectures and seminars as well as the practical engagement in exercise sessions, tutorials and studios. In the scope of this study, GBL should address the way students interact with the solution of tasks to better understand the process. Moreover, as the retrospective reviewing of content appears to be one of the major problems, the scenario to be developed should assist students in their entire learning process and, therefore, provide different levels of difficulty that can be useful throughout the first semesters.

Another objective pursued in the development of a suitable GBL scenario should rest on the enhancement of students' ability to choose adequate LS. As noted by Jonassen (17), one of the advantages of a game world is that it enables learners to immerse themselves in another reality and adopt its rules. It is via these rules that learning content can be mediated without directly addressing it as such (18). Thus, by embedding it in a coherent game world the abstract problem area could be rendered more tangible for students and comprehension could be increased. The personal experience and (embodied) actions of players can strengthen a sense of relevance that supports the learning behaviour (17, 10) – and may increase the use of cognitively deep LS. On the other hand, the world portrayed in a game is

abstracted into a model and can thereby simplify the learning process similar to the teaching strategies already employed to convey the basics of EM (18). In this way, an interactive learning scenario would allow the link between idealised learning content and practical application. By drawing on both, effects of flow and immersion as well as direct feedback mechanisms, learners could be motivated to playfully solve problems in an experimental low risk environment. Once again, tangibility could be increased and complexity reduced.

Insights gained from engaging with a game world can also lead to a change in attitude, which is linked to tendencies of shifting one's action and attention towards the subject matter. GBL can facilitate such a deep engagement on various levels and help automating specific solving patterns (10). In order to do so, content would need to be designed and structured in a way that supports the use of cognitively deep and meta-cognitive LS as well as resources. A special emphasis should be placed on students whose first language is not German and their use of resources such as cooperation with peers and additional support offered by the university. Among other things, this can be achieved by evoking positive emotions via reward systems and adapting the scenario to different needs – an aspect that is of special importance in the face of the diverse student body in engineering courses. However, it is important to keep the transferability of gained knowledge and skills onto actual exam situations in mind (19).

6 OUTLOOK

Game-based learning environments have the potential to convey complex subject matters in a more tangible way. Given their various functionalities, they can support the entire learning process from activating prior knowledge to facilitating exam preparation. The empirical data gathered from the survey presented here will help to determine at what point in time the learning scenario will be put to use and how it needs to be designed. As of the data gathered and analysed up to this point the greatest demand appears to lie in the preparation of future learning as well as the training of existing skills and knowledge. Although differences in the learning process proved to be only minor in this study, it is still pertinent to design the scenario in an adaptive way so that it can respond to the increasing diversity of students' backgrounds, interests and needs regardless of whether they are gender-, language- or education-specific. In the next project phase, design concepts and prototypes devised on the basis of the obtained data will be evaluated together with the target group. In this way, the Learn&Play project responds to Hoblitz's postulation to investigate further the tension between gaming and learning experience by producing process-oriented results which can be seen as a basis for further developments in the field of technical knowledge and its forms of dissemination in academic contexts (12).

7 ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The project is funded by the European Social Fund (ESF) and the Federal State of Brandenburg via the Brandenburg Ministry for Labour, Social Affairs, Health, Women and Family (MASGF).

REFERENCES

- [1] Heublein U., Richter J., Schmelzer R. and Simmer D., (2014), Die Entwicklung der Studienabbruchquoten an den deutschen Hochschulen. Statistische Berechnungen auf der Basis des Absolventenjahrgangs 2012, *HIS: Forum Hochschule 4*, Hannover, pp. 1718-1731.
- [2] Zander H., (2013), Man darf sich in diesem Studium nicht von den Herausforderungen schrecken lassen, *VDI nachrichten, Vol. 38*, <https://www.vdi-nachrichten.com/Management-Karriere/Man-in-Studium-Herausforderungen-schrecken-lassen>.
- [3] Dammann E., (2016), *Entwicklung eines Testinstruments zur Messung fachlicher Kompetenzen in der Technischen Mechanik bei Studierenden ingenieurwissenschaftlicher Studiengänge*, Dissertationsschrift, Stuttgart.
- [4] Adelman C., (1998), *Women and Men of the Engineering Path: A Model for Analyses of Undergraduate Careers*, US Government Printing Office, Superintendent of Documents, Mail Stop: SSOP, Washington, DC 20402-9328.
- [5] Ripke M. and Siegeris J., (2012), Informatik–ein Männerfach!?, *Informatik-Spektrum, Vol. 35, No. 5*, pp. 331-338.
- [6] Weinstein C. E. and Mayer R. E., (1986), *The teaching of learning strategies, Handbook of research on teaching*, M. Wittrock (ed.), Macmillan, New York, pp. 315-327.
- [7] Wild K.-P., (2000), *Lernstrategien im Studium. Strukturen und Bedingungen*, Münster: Waxmann.
- [8] Wild K.-P., (2005), Individuelle Lernstrategien von Studierenden. Konsequenzen für die Hochschuldidaktik und die Hochschullehre, *Beiträge zur Lehrerinnen- und Lehrerbildung, Vol. 23, No. 2*, pp. 191-206.
- [9] Le S., Weber P. and Ebner, M., (2013), *Game-Based Learning. Lehrbuch für Lernen und Lehren mit Technologien: 2. Auflage*, <http://l3t.eu/homepage/das-buch/ebook-2013>.

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- [10] Plass J. L., Homer B. D. and Kinzer C. K., (2015), Foundations of Game-Based Learning, *Educational Psychologist*, Vol. 50, No. 4, pp. 258–283.
- [11] Wouters P. and van Oostendorp H., (2013), A meta-analytic review of the role of instructional support in game-based learning, *Computers & Education*, Vol. 60, No. 1, pp. 412-425.
- [12] Hoblitz A., (2014), *Spielend Lernen im Flow: Die motivationale Wirkung von Serious Games im Schulunterricht*, Springer-Verlag, Paderborn, p. 8.
- [13] Wagner, M. and Mitgutsch K., (2008), *Didaktische Szenarien des Digital Game Based Learning*. Endbericht des Projekts, Donau-Universität Krems.
- [14] Egenfeldt-Nielsen S., (2006), Overview of Research on the Educational Use of Video Games, *Digital Kompetenz*, Vol. 1, No. 3, p. 202.
- [15] Narciss S., Sosnovsky S., Schnaubert L., Andrès E., Eichelmann A., Gogvadze G. and Melis E., (2014), Exploring feedback and student characteristics relevant for personalizing feedback strategies, *Computers & Education*, Vol. 71, pp. 56-76.
- [16] Wild K. P. and Schiefele U., (1994), Lernstrategien im Studium: Ergebnisse zur Faktorenstruktur und Reliabilität eines neuen Fragebogens, *Zeitschrift für differentielle und diagnostische Psychologie*, Vol.15, No. 4, pp.185-200.
- [17] Jonassen D. H., (2006), On the Role of Concepts in Learning and Instructional Design, *Educational Technology Research and Development*, Vol. 54, No. 2, p. 177.
- [18] Shaffer D. W., Halverson R., Squire K. R. and Gee J. P., (2005), Video Games and the Future of Learning, *WCER Working Paper*, No. 2005-4.
- [19] Frey R. C., (2012), *Computer Games as Preparation for Future Learning, Assessment in Game-Based Learning*, Springer, New York, pp. 431-451